

Some Prime Labeling Results of H -Class Graphs

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Abstract: Prime labeling originated with Entringer and was introduced by Tout, Dabboucy and Howalla [3]. A Graph $G(V, E)$ is said to have a *prime labeling* if its vertices are labeled with distinct integers $1, 2, 3, \dots, |V(G)|$ such that for each edge xy the labels assigned to x and y are relatively prime. A graph admits a prime labeling is called a *prime graph*. We investigate the prime labeling of some H -class graphs.

Key Words: labeling, prime labeling, prime graph, H -class graph

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§1. Introduction

A simple graph $G(V, E)$ is said to have a prime labeling (or called prime) if its vertices are labeled with distinct integers $1, 2, 3, \dots, |V(G)|$, such that for each edge $xy \in E(G)$, the labels assigned to x and y are relatively prime [1].

We begin with listing a few definitions/notations that are used.

(1) A graph $G = (V, E)$ is said to have order $|V|$ and size $|E|$.

(2) A vertex $v \in V(G)$ of degree 1 is called pendant vertex.

(3) P_n is a path of length n .

(4) The H -graph is defined as the union of two paths of length n together with an edge joining the mid points of them. That is, it is obtained from two copies of P_n with vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ and $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n$ by joining the vertices $v_{(n+1)/2}$ and $u_{(n+1)/2}$ by means of an edge if n is odd and the vertices $v_{(n/2)+1}$ and $u_{n/2}$ if n is even [4].

(5) The corona $G_1 \odot G_2$ of two graphs G_1 and G_2 is defined as the graph G obtained by taking one copy of G_1 (which has p_1 points) and p_1 copies of G_2 and then joining the i^{th} point of G_1 to every point in the i^{th} copy of G_2 [1].

§2. Prime Labeling of H -Class Graphs

Theorem 2.1 *The H -graph of a path of length n is prime.*

Proof Let $G = (V, E)$ be a H -graph of a path of length n . It is obtained from two copies

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of paths of length n . It has $2n$ vertices and $2n - 1$ edges.

$$V(G) = \{u_i, v_i / 1 \leq i \leq n\}$$

$$E(G) = \{u_i u_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1} / 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\} \cup \{u_{\lceil n/2 \rceil} v_{\lceil n/2 \rceil}\}$$

Define $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 2n\}$ by

$$f(v_{(n+1)/2}) = 1 \text{ if } n \text{ is odd}$$

$$f(v_{n/2}) = 1 \text{ if } n \text{ is even}$$

$$f(u_i) = i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_i) = n + i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq (n/2) - 1, \text{ when } i \neq (n/2) \text{ if } n \text{ is even}$$

$$f(v_i) = n + i, (n/2) + 1 \leq i \leq n, \text{ if } n \text{ is even}$$

$$f(v_i) = n + i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq (n - 1)/2, \text{ when } i \neq (n + 1)/2, \text{ if } n \text{ is odd}$$

$$f(v_i) = n + i, (n + 3)/2 \leq i \leq n, \text{ when } i \neq (n + 1)/2, \text{ if } n \text{ is odd}$$

Clearly, it is easy to check that $GCD(f(u), f(v)) = 1$, for every edge $uv \in E(G)$. Therefore, the H -graph of a path of length n admits prime labeling. $\square$

Example 2.2 The prime labeling for H -graph with $n = 14, 16$ are shown in Fig.1 and 2.

Fig.1 $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$

Fig.2 $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$

Theorem 2.3 *The graph $G \odot K_1$ is a prime.*

Proof $G \odot K_1$ is obtained from H -graph by attaching pendant vertices to each of the

vertices. The graph has $4n$ vertices and $4n - 1$ edges, where $n = |G|$.

$$V(G \odot K_1) = \{u_i, v_i / 1 \leq i \leq 2n\}$$

$$E(G \odot K_1) = \{u_i u_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1} / 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_i u_{n+i}, v_i v_{n+i} / 1 \leq i \leq n\}$$

$$\cup \{u_{(n+1)/2} v_{(n+1)/2} \text{ } n \text{ is odd or } u_{(n/2)+1} v_{n/2}, n \text{ is even.}\}$$

Define $f : V(G \odot K_1) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 4n\}$ by

$$f(u_i) = 2i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq n \text{ and } \begin{cases} i \neq (n+1)/2 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ i \neq n/2 & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

$$f(u_{(n+1)/2}) = 1 \text{ } n \text{ odd}$$

$$f(u_{(n/2)+1}) = 1 \text{ } n \text{ even}$$

$$f(u_{n+i}) = 2i, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_i) = 2n + 2i - 1, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_{n+i}) = 2n + 2i, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$GCD(f(u_i), f(u_{i+1})) = GCD(2i + 1, 2i + 3) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq (n-3)/2, n \text{ odd}$$

$$GCD(f(u_i), f(u_{i+1})) = GCD(2i + 1, 2i + 3) = 1, (n+3)/2 \leq i \leq n-1, n \text{ odd}$$

$$GCD(f(u_i), f(u_{i+1})) = GCD(2i + 1, 2i + 3) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq (n/2) - 1, n \text{ even}$$

$$GCD(f(u_i), f(u_{i+1})) = GCD(2i + 1, 2i + 3) = 1, (n/2) + 2 \leq i \leq n-1, n \text{ even}$$

$$GCD(f(v_i), f(v_{i+1})) = GCD(2n + 2i - 1, 2n + 2i + 1) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$GCD(f(v_i), f(v_{n+i})) = GCD(2n + 2i - 1, 2n + 2i) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq n.$$

In this case it can be easily verified that $GCD(f(u), f(v)) = 1$ for remaining edges $uv \in E(G \odot K_1)$. Therefore, $G \odot K_1$ admits prime labeling. $\square$

Example 2.4 The prime labeling for $G \odot K_1$ and $G \odot K_1$ are shown in Fig.3 and 4.

Fig.3 $G \odot K_1$

Fig.4 $G \odot K_1$

Theorem 2.5 *The graph $G \odot S_2$ is prime.*

Proof The graph $G \odot S_2$ has $6n$ vertices and $6n - 1$ edges, where $n = |G|$.

$$\begin{aligned} V(G \odot S_2) &= \{u_i, v_i/1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_i^{(1)}, u_i^{(2)}, v_i^{(1)}, v_i^{(2)}/1 \leq i \leq n\} \\ E(G \odot S_2) &= \{u_i u_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1}/1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_i u_i^{(1)}, u_i u_i^{(2)}, v_i v_i^{(1)}, v_i v_i^{(2)}/1 \leq i \leq n\} \\ &\cup \{u_{n+1/2} v_{n+1/2} \text{ } n \text{ is odd or } u_{n/2+1} v_{n/2} \text{ } n \text{ is even.} \end{aligned}$$

Define $f : V \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 6n\}$ by

$$f(u_{n+1/2}) = 1, f(u_{(n+1)/2}^{(1)}) = 6n - 1, f(u_{(n+1)/2}^{(2)}) = 6n.$$

Case 1 Suppose $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$.

Subcase 1.1 $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_{2i-1}) &= 6(i-1) + 3, 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/4 \\ f(u_{2i-1}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 6 + 6[i - ((n-1)/4) + 2], \\ &\quad ((n-1)/4) + 2 \leq i \leq ((n-1)/2) + 1 \\ f(u_{2i}) &= 6(i-1) + 5, 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/4 \\ f(u_{2i}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 4 + 6[i - ((n-1)/4) + 1], \\ &\quad ((n-1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\ f(u_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(u_1) - 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/4 \\ f(u_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 7 + 6[i - ((n-1)/4) + 2], \\ &\quad ((n-1)/4) + 2 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\ f(u_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(u_1) + 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/4 \\ f(u_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 8 + 6[i - ((n-1)/4) + 2], \\ &\quad ((n-1)/4) + 2 \leq i \leq ((n-1)/2) + 1 \\ f(u_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(u_2) + 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/4 \\ f(u_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 3 + 6[i - ((n-1)/4) + 1], \\ &\quad ((n-1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\ f(u_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(u_2) + 2 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/4 \\ f(u_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 5 + 6[i - ((n-1)/4) + 1], \\ &\quad ((n-1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\ f(v_1) &= 3n, f(v_2) = 3n + 2 \\ f(v_{2i-1}) &= f(v_1) + 6(i-1), 2 \leq i \leq (n+1)/2 \\ f(v_{2i}) &= f(v_2) + 6(i-1), 2 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\ f(v_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(v_1) - 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n+1)/2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f(v_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(v_1) + 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n+1)/2 \\
f(v_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(v_2) + 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\
f(v_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(v_2) + 2 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\
GCD(f(u_{2i-1}), f(u_{2i})) &= GCD(6i-3, 6i-1) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/4 \\
GCD(f(u_{2i}), f(u_{2i+1})) &= GCD(6i-1, 6i+3) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq ((n-1)/4) - 1 \\
GCD(f(u_{2i-1}), f(u_{2i})) &= GCD(6i-7, 6i-3) = 1, \\
&\quad ((n-1)/4) + 2 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\
GCD(f(u_{2i}), f(u_{2i+1})) &= GCD(6i-3, 6i-1) = 1, \\
&\quad ((n-1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\
GCD(f(u_{2i-1}), f(u_{2i-1}^{(2)})) &= GCD(6i-7, 6i-5) = 1, \\
&\quad ((n-1)/4) + 2 \leq i \leq ((n-1)/2) + 1 \\
GCD(f(u_{2i}), f(u_{2i}^{(2)})) &= GCD(6i-1, 6i+1) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/4 \\
GCD(f(u_{2i}), f(u_{2i}^{(2)})) &= GCD(6i-3, 6i-2) = 1, \\
&\quad ((n-1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\
GCD(f(v_1), f(v_2)) &= GCD(3n, 3n+2) = 1 \\
GCD(f(v_{2i-1}), f(v_{2i})) &= GCD(3n+6i-6, 3n+6i-4) = 1, \\
&\quad 2 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\
GCD(f(v_{2i}), f(v_{2i+1})) &= GCD(3n+6i-4, 3n+6i) = 1, \\
&\quad 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2 \\
GCD(f(v_{2i}), f(v_{2i}^{(2)})) &= GCD(3n+6i-4, 3n+6i-2) = 1, \\
&\quad 1 \leq i \leq (n-1)/2.
\end{aligned}$$

Subcase 1.2 $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$

$$\begin{aligned}
f(u_{2i-1}) &= 6(i-1) + 3, 1 \leq i \leq (n+1)/4 \\
f(u_{2i-1}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 2 + 6[i - ((n+1)/4) + 1], \\
&\quad ((n+1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq (n+1)/2 \\
f(u_{2i}) &= 6(i-1) + 5, 1 \leq i \leq ((n+1)/4) - 1 \\
f(u_{2i}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 6 + 6[i - ((n+1)/4) + 1], \\
&\quad ((n+1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq ((n+1)/2) - 1 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(u_1) - 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n+1)/4 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 3 + 6[i - ((n+1)/4) + 1], \\
&\quad ((n+1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq (n+1)/2 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(u_1) + 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n+1)/4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f(u_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 4 + 6[i - ((n+1)/4) + 1], \\
&\quad ((n+1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq (n+1)/2 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(u_2) + 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq ((n+1)/4) - 1 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 5 + 6[i - ((n+1)/4) + 1], \\
&\quad ((n+1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq ((n+1)/2) - 1 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(u_2) + 2 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq ((n+1)/4) - 1 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(u_{(n-1)/2}) + 7 + 6[i - ((n+1)/4) + 1], \\
&\quad ((n+1)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq ((n+1)/2) - 1 \\
f(v_1) &= 3n, f(v_2) = 3n + 2 \\
f(v_{2i-1}) &= f(v_1) + 6(i-1), 2 \leq i \leq (n+1)/2 \\
f(v_{2i}) &= f(v_2) + 6(i-1), 2 \leq i \leq ((n+1)/2) - 1 \\
f(v_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(v_1) - 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n+1)/2 \\
f(v_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(v_1) + 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq (n+1)/2 \\
f(v_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(v_2) + 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq ((n+1)/2) - 1 \\
f(v_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(v_2) + 2 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq ((n+1)/2) - 1.
\end{aligned}$$

As in the above case it can be verified that $GCD(f(u), f(v)) = 1$ for every edge $uv \in E(G \odot S_2)$.

Case 2. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$

$$f(u_{(n/2)+1}) = 1, f(u_{(n/2)+1}^{(1)}) = 6n - 1, f(u_{(n/2)+1}^{(2)}) = 6n.$$

Subcase 2.1 $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$

$$\begin{aligned}
f(u_{2i-1}) &= 6(i-1) + 3, 1 \leq i \leq n/4 \\
f(u_{2i-1}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 6 + 6[i - (n/4) + 2], (n/4) + 2 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(u_{2i}) &= 6(i-1) + 5, 1 \leq i \leq n/4 \\
f(u_{2i}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 4 + 6[i - (n/4) + 1], (n/4) + 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(u_1) - 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq n/4 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 7 + 6[i - (n/4) + 2], (n/4) + 2 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(u_1) + 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq n/4 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 8 + 6[i - (n/4) + 2], (n/4) + 2 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(u_2) + 1 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq n/4 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 3 + 6[i - (n/4) + 1], (n/4) + 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(u_2) + 2 + 6(i-1), 1 \leq i \leq n/4 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 5 + 6[i - (n/4) + 1], (n/4) + 1 \leq i \leq n/2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f(v_1) &= 3n - 1, f(v_2) = 3(n + 1) \\
f(v_{2i-1}) &= f(v_1) + 6(i - 1), 2 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_{2i}) &= f(v_2) + 6(i - 1), 2 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(v_1) + 1 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(v_1) + 2 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(v_2) - 1 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(v_2) + 1 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq n/2
\end{aligned}$$

Clearly $GCD(f(u), f(v)) = 1$ for every edge $uv \in E(G \odot S_2)$.

Subcase 2.2 $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$

$$\begin{aligned}
f(u_{2i-1}) &= 6(i - 1) + 3, 1 \leq i \leq (n + 2)/4 \\
f(u_{2i-1}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 2 + 6[i - ((n + 2)/4) + 1], ((n + 2)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(u_{2i}) &= 6(i - 1) + 5, 1 \leq i \leq (n - 2)/4 \\
f(u_{2i}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 6 + 6[i - ((n - 2)/4) + 2], ((n - 2)/4) + 2 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(u_1) - 1 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq (n + 2)/4 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 3 + 6[i - ((n + 2)/4) + 1], ((n + 2)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(u_1) + 1 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq (n + 2)/4 \\
f(u_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 4 + 6[i - ((n + 2)/4) + 1], ((n + 2)/4) + 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(u_2) + 1 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq (n - 2)/4 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 5 + 6[i - ((n - 2)/4) + 2], ((n - 2)/4) + 2 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(u_2) + 2 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq (n - 2)/4 \\
f(u_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(u_{(n/2)}) + 7 + 6[i - ((n - 2)/4) + 2], ((n - 2)/4) + 2 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_1) &= 3n - 1, f(v_2) = 3(n + 1) \\
f(v_{2i-1}) &= f(v_1) + 6(i - 1), 2 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_{2i}) &= f(v_2) + 6(i - 1), 2 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_{2i-1}^{(1)}) &= f(v_1) + 1 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_{2i-1}^{(2)}) &= f(v_1) + 2 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_{2i}^{(1)}) &= f(v_2) - 1 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq n/2 \\
f(v_{2i}^{(2)}) &= f(v_2) + 1 + 6(i - 1), 1 \leq i \leq n/2.
\end{aligned}$$

In this case also it is easy to check that $GCD(f(u), f(v)) = 1$. Therefore $G \odot S_2$ admits prime labeling. $\square$

Example 2.6 The prime labelings for $G \odot S_2$ with $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ are respectively shown in Fig.5-8 following.

Fig.5 $G \odot S_2$ $n \equiv 1(\text{mod}4)$

Fig.6 $G \odot S_2$ $n \equiv 3(\text{mod}4)$

Fig.7 $G \odot S_2$ $n \equiv 0(\text{mod}4)$

Fig.8 $G \odot S_2$ $n \equiv 2(\text{mod}4)$

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